

Optimised Synthesis of Rhombic dodecahedral Cu₂O Nanoparticles: A Pathway to Superior Morphological Control

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Cuprous oxide (Cu₂O) nanoparticles hold significant promise for photocatalytic applications due to their narrow bandgap and high surface reactivity. This study focuses on the synthesis of rhombic dodecahedral Cu₂O (RD-Cu₂O) nanoparticles, totally enclosed by {110} facets, known to exhibit superior photocatalytic performance over the other low-index crystallographic facets. The precise control over the synthesis conditions can significantly enhance the exposure of this highly active face and therefore improve the catalytic performance of Cu₂O nanoparticles, making them superior for applications in pollutant degradation, organic reactions, and artificial photosynthesis. We systematically optimised the synthesis parameters, including

reactants concentration, pH and other reaction conditions, to achieve a significant scale up of well-defined RD-Cu₂O nanoparticles production, strictly necessary for the use of this photocatalyst on a larger scale. The optimised and scaled up synthesis require 2.0 mmol of CuCl₂, 6.0 mmol of Sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS), 9.6 mmol of NH₂OH·HCl and 7.0 mmol of NaOH added in this order to 400 ml of water at 25 °C. The optimised nanoparticles demonstrated a narrow size distribution and a high degree of crystallographic control. Characterisation techniques such as FESEM, XRD, EPR, UV-Vis spectroscopy, and XPS confirmed the improved morphological and structural properties of the synthesised RD-Cu₂O nanoparticles.

Introduction

Cuprous oxide (or cuprite, Cu₂O) is a p-type semiconductor that has attracted great interest in different applications thanks to its unique optical, electrical and magnetic properties, plus to its low-cost, nontoxicity, earth abundance and easy synthesis.^[1–4] In the last decades^[5–11] it's more and more considered highly promising in photo(electro)catalysis since it's able to absorb visible light, thanks to the narrow direct bandgap (2.0–2.3 eV), and possess a highly reducing potential at the conduction-band edge.^[6] In particular Cu₂O nanoparticles are considered a very promising material in visible-light photocatalysis, with application in pollutants degradation, organic reactions, CO oxidation, H₂ evolution (water splitting), CO₂ photo-reduction (Artificial-Photosynthesis) and organic reactions.^[8,12–17] The solid crystallises in a simple cubic structure with space group Pn-3 m and can be interpreted as an interpenetration of two sub-lattice, the face-centered cubic (fcc) sub-lattice of the Cu⁺ ions and the

body-centered cubic (bcc) sub-lattice of the O²⁻ ions. Thus, the crystal structure results in a unit cell with four Cu⁺ bicoordinated and two O²⁻ tetraordinated.^[18] This material shows strong shape-dependent properties, due to the different crystallographic planes exposed on the surface.^[5,6] The more common and stable shapes are the ones fully enclosed with only one (low-index) facet, namely cubic (C-Cu₂O), with six {100} facets; octahedral (O-Cu₂O), with eight {111} facets; and rhombic dodecahedral (RD-Cu₂O), with twelve {110} facets exposed on the surface. Among all, RD-Cu₂O particles are largely reported to be those with the best photocatalytic activity, probably due to small band bending towards the surface that ensure a negligible energy barrier and that enables a good electron and hole mobility to and on the surface.^[5,19–21] Moreover, the {110} facet, on the Cu-terminated layer, shows only coordinately unsaturated Copper ions, typically ensuring better adsorption behaviour.^[22] The synthesis of particles with controlled shapes is a delicate art that relies on finding the right balance of reaction conditions to promote the growth of particles along the desired direction. Upon the addition of growth units, the crystalline seed generated through nucleation tends to grow along a specific direction at a rate proportional to the anisotropic chemical bonding energy density of the single crystal.^[23] In other words, the shape of crystals grown under or near equilibrium conditions is primarily governed by surface free energies. Based on these concepts, it is intuitive to understand that promoting crystal growth along the desired direction relies on the reaction conditions capable of selectively stabilising the crystallographic face that is worth to be expressed on the particle's surface. Cu₂O particles typical synthesis consists in reduction and precipitation of a Cu²⁺ precursor, and requires basic environment in at least one step of the reaction

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to pass via the $[\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_4]^{2-}$ intermediate. This type of reaction was used also in qualitative analysis for determining the reducing aldehydes, namely Fehling's and Benedict's tests, whose reagents consist of Copper(II) ions in alkaline solution with a complexing agent to prevent precipitation of $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$, *i.e.* tartrate and citrate ions respectively. In the last two decades a lot of variants of this type of reactions have been proposed to obtain particles with different size and morphology, changing Cu precursor, reducing agent, solvent, temperature, pH and/or additives; moreover, different type of surfactant agents were added in different concentration to obtain particles with well-defined shape and control with precision the (low index) facet exposed on the surface.^[9,15,24–40] The use of surfactants as a control factor is one of the most effective methods, but their significant drawback lies in the potential difficulty of removing these molecules from the surface at the end of the synthesis. This is essential to free the catalytically active surface and prevent reaction by-products associated with these molecules.^[6] Strong acid, strong base, and high-temperature treatments should be avoided because they can result in particles sintering, etching or dislocation of surface atoms toward more stable surfaces, leading to the loss of the desired shape. Therefore, the only suitable method involves consecutive sonication steps with large amounts of solvents and centrifugation to collect the nanoparticles. In this regard, the only two solvents that appear to be easily washable are trisodium citrate and Sodium Dodecyl Sulphate (SDS). In fact, for these capping agents, washes with a 1:1 mixture of water and ethanol are sufficient.^[6,22,41] Taking these considerations into account, the only synthesis that appears suitable for the production of RD- Cu_2O nanoparticles is the one developed by Michael H. Huang *et al.* In this synthesis, SDS is employed as the surfactant, while $\text{NH}_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{HCl}$ serves as the reducing agent. Beyond its role in promoting the reduction to Cu_2O , it also seems to play a role in stabilising the {110} surface.^[24] In this study, an exhaustive investigation of every parameter of the synthesis was conducted to identify the optimal reaction conditions. By fine-tuning the reaction parameters, we achieved improved nanoparticle definition, a slightly reduction in size, and an increase in the yield. Furthermore, we successfully scaled up the reaction to 2 mmol of reactant while maintaining approximately the same level of particle definition. This is a critical feature for a material with shape-dependent properties, as it ensures the presence of a single type of crystallographic plane on the surface. On one hand, this enables the accurate attribution of the material reactivity to the specific crystallographic face, and on the other hand, it ensures the highest extent of the most catalytically active surface.

Experimental Section

In a typical synthesis, as reported in literature,^[24] a certain amount of Sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) was dissolved in deionized water in a beaker with magnetic stirring, then a certain volume of CuCl_2 1 M, NaOH 5 M and $\text{NH}_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{HCl}$ 1 M was quickly added. The solution was stirred for 10 seconds and then left aging. When CuCl_2 is added to the water the solution colour changes from uncoloured to light blue, after the adding of NaOH it quickly changes in deep

blue and after adding $\text{NH}_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{HCl}$ it becomes green. After a while the solution starts to turn to yellow and then, finally, to orange at the end of the aging with some orange precipitate at the bottom of the beaker, indicating the Cu_2O nanoparticles formation. The process of colour evolution from green to orange took about 10 minutes, as previously reported, and the slow rate of the colour change between green and orange suggests that the nanoparticles have a rhombic dodecahedral shape.^[24] The precipitate was collected by centrifugation at 2500 RCF for 10 minutes and then washed several times with a mixture of water and ethanol to remove unreacted chemicals and SDS surfactant. Then it was left to dry at room temperature. To evaluate the effect of the different conditions an optimisation study has been carried out, varying different conditions (Table S1). The reference reaction conditions, on which optimization of the parameters was conducted, are listed in the table with the entry "0" and are in line with the method outlined by M.H. Huang *et al.*,^[24] except that the reagent quantities and the volume utilised are proportionately multiplied by 4, as to ensure sufficient amount of product to conduct the appropriate characterization analyses.

Results and Discussion

RD- Cu_2O Nanoparticles Optimization

RD- Cu_2O nanoparticles synthesised with the reported methodology,^[24] scaled up to 4x, resulted in being poor defined, with a broad size distribution, in a range of 1 to 2 μm (Figure 1). In order to achieve more precisely defined and smaller RD-nanoparticles, adjustments were made to the synthesis conditions, with a focus on maximising the surface area of the most catalytically active {110} crystallographic plane across all nanoparticles. All the synthesised nanoparticles discussed below exhibit a clear and similar Cu_2O XRD pattern

Figure 1. Cu_2O particles obtained by a 4x scale-up of the procedure used as reference.^[24]

(Figure S1) indicating highly crystalline structure and no other compounds (unless specified otherwise). The optimization criteria in the following sections are based on the FESEM images of the nanoparticles, aiming to identify conditions that lead to the smallest and best-defined RD-nanoparticles.

Effect of Drying Mode and Temperature of the Reaction

Since the size and morphology of nanoparticles are typically closely tied to the applied pressure and temperature,^[42] the initial parameters under examination were the drying pressure and the reaction temperature. Conducting the drying process in ambient air resulted in the production of smaller nanoparticles, typically falling within the range of 400–500 nm. In specific cases, these displayed a well-defined RD shape. However, some nanoparticles retained an undefined shape with a rough surface (Figure S2B).

The enhancement in the definition and size of the nanoparticles could be attributed to the absence of vacuum conditions. The presence of a vacuum environment can potentially lead to nanoparticle collapse due to the reduced pressure within the sample tube. To investigate the impact of the temperature on the reaction, a reaction at 293 K (room temperature) was initially conducted resulting in poorly defined spherical-like nanoparticles (Figure S2C). At this temperature, a longer duration is required for nanoparticle formation, evidenced by the slower colour change from green to light orange occurring after 3 hours. An intermediate temperature of 298 K was also tested. Figure S2D presents the outcomes after allowing the reaction to proceed for 1 hour post the emergence of the orange colour, 2 hours (Figure S2E), or terminating it immediately (Figure S2F). The latter case proved to be superior, yielding smaller nanoparticles, approximately 200–430 nm in size, with an apparent narrow size distribution and a better-defined RD-shape. Higher temperatures are directly associated with faster kinetics, likely causing a rearrangement of the particle surface. In contrast, lower temperatures are linked to slower kinetics, allowing for more precise nanoparticle formation. However, if the reaction is excessively slow, particle etching can occur in the slightly acidic environment.^[34]

Effect of Injection Order of Reagents

To investigate the influence of reagents addition order in the reaction mixture, two distinct experiments were undertaken (Figure S3). In the first experiment CuCl_2 was introduced before SDS. This resulted in no observable changes in nanoparticle morphology but contributed to a slightly improved yield (+15%). This enhancement can be ascribed to the improved dissolution of the Cu precursor in water, preventing its entrapment on the surface by the surfactant micelle. In the second experiment the order of $\text{NH}_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{HCl}$ was interchanged with NaOH. It is noteworthy that in this experiment, the solution colour began changing only after the addition of the base, highlighting its crucial role in initiating the entire reaction. This

observation suggests that the reducing agent is ineffective at excessively acidic pH. The reaction produced a nearly mono-dispersed sample with well-defined RD-nanoparticles (Figure 2A). This progress may be attributed to the better dispersion of the reducing agent in the solution before the initiation of the reaction.

Effect of the Amount of Reagents

Investigating the interdependence of the relative quantities of the other reagents, with copper as a reference, proves to be a valuable inquiry. As highlighted in the introduction, a comprehensive analysis of the impact of the reducing agent's relative amount has been undertaken, elucidating its pivotal role in shaping the nanoparticles.^[24] In this context, the obtained results from syntheses, wherein the quantities of SDS, NaOH and $\text{NH}_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{HCl}$ at fixed pH were systematically altered, are presented below.

Figure 2. Visual decreasing of corner etching for RD-Nanoparticles along optimisation; A) 1.2 mmol SDS, pH = 5.7; B) 0.6 mmol SDS, pH = 5.7; C) 0.6 mmol SDS, pH = 5.5.

SDS

The surfactant's role in synthesis varies based on several factors, including the type of reaction (such as Sol-gel, Hydrothermal, Emulsion, etc...), pH, solvent, and surfactant peculiarities (charge, shape, tail length, functional group, and concentration).^[43–46] Its behaviour generally falls into two categories: micelle formation and adsorption.^[43]

In the studied reaction, particularly with low SDS concentration, its role appears to be a mix of both. In fact, at the employed SDS concentration, micelle formation is considered favourable,^[47–50] but on the other hand SDS exhibits a selective adsorption role, restraining the growth of specific facets and thereby influencing particle morphology.

While existing studies, notably A. Nathan *et al.*,^[22] only present three cases (0, 3.5, and 7 equivalents of Copper precursor), our work explores a broader range of SDS amounts. Tests were conducted, varying SDS from 0 to 2 mmol in 0.2 mmol increments, while maintaining other conditions constant. All resulting nanoparticle images are depicted in Figure S4.

When no SDS is added to the reaction (Figure S4A), the colour change occurs in less than 10 minutes, resulting in small, undefined particles, highlighting its critical role in controlling particle morphology.

As observed for the other cases (Figure S4B–J), the nanoparticles retained dimensions across the series, with subtle changes in morphology. Furthermore, there was a subtle reduction in reaction yield as SDS amounts increased, probably due to the capture of Cu^{+2+} ions from SDS micelle. Among the samples, the one figured in Figure 2B represents the optimal trade-off being the most defined and homogeneous, with a slightly better yield. Subsequent tests retained the SDS amount equivalent to that sample, *i.e.* 3 equivalents regarding the Cu^{2+} amount.

NaOH

Literature has extensively explored the impact of the relative amount of NaOH in similar types of reactions, focusing on both particle size and morphology.^[9,25,26,28–31] To investigate this further, we conducted various tests by altering the NaOH amount while keeping other conditions constant, ranging from 0 to 0.9 mmol with increments of 0.1 mmol each time. All resulting FESEM images are presented in Figure S5.

Below 0.4 mmol of NaOH, the reaction failed, yielding no detectable product. In the remaining samples, no significant changes in dimensions were observed, but the pH notably influenced particle morphology.

At lower pH (lower NaOH amounts), particles appeared “destroyed” and deeply etched, possibly due to the acidic environment according to [Equation (1)].^[51] Conversely, at higher pH (greater NaOH amounts), particles exhibited a bevelled morphology, as previously reported.^[26]

The reaction demonstrated highly sensitivity to solution pH, with a slight improvement in definition, remarkably with no visible etching on the rhombic-dodecahedron corners, and yield observed for the sample in Figure 2C, with 3,5 equivalents with respect to Cu^{2+} amount, now considered as the reference for subsequent tests.

$\text{NH}_2\text{OH} \cdot \text{HCl}$ at fixed pH

Given the critical role of acidity in the reaction, with an optimal pH around 5.5 identified as the ideal compromise, it has been established as the standard pH for subsequent experiments. In these tests, the quantity of $\text{NH}_2\text{OH} \cdot \text{HCl}$ was varied, adjusting the amount of NaOH to maintain a reaction pH of 5.5. However, the quantity of $\text{NH}_2\text{OH} \cdot \text{HCl}$ (relative to Cu^{2+}) has proven equally crucial, as previously outlined.^[22] As depicted in Figure S6, different amounts of this reducing agent resulted in a deterioration in the definition and size of nanoparticles or in {100}-truncated rhombododecahedral nanoparticles (Figure S6C).

The reason for the necessity of exactly 4,8 equivalents of this reducing agent for the reduction of Cu^{2+} remains unclear.

Effect of Reaction Volume

The reaction volume directly influences the absolute concentration of the reagents, which is crucial for the kinetics of the reaction. Here, a study was conducted on the optimal reaction volume by varying the water volume while keeping the remaining conditions unchanged. The screening was performed from 10 ml to 80 ml, with increments of 10 ml between each test. All reactions, except the one conducted in 10 ml, resulted in a successful reaction outcome. However, as illustrated in Figure S7, volumes less than 40 ml led to agglomerates of nanoparticles, indicating the development of rhombododecahedral nanoparticles from closely spaced crystalline seeds that joined during growth. Conversely, volumes exceeding 40 ml produced identical results with well-separated nanoparticles but with sizes twice that of the reference standard.

This result indicates that a volume of 40 ml is already optimal for the examined reaction. It represents the minimum volume sufficient to have nanoparticles adequately separated and of the minimum achievable size.

This implies a challenge in up-scaling the reaction, given the large solvent volumes needed to ensure correct absolute concentrations of reagents. This makes it technically difficult to maintain the homogeneity of reaction conditions, primarily local concentrations and temperature, throughout the entire batch. In this regard, adopting a continuous-flow reaction approach could be the optimal solution to obtain larger quantities of material while ensuring homogeneity of reaction parameters and, consequently, the outcome.^[15]

Unfortunately, the extended reaction time required for the examined reaction makes the creation of such a system not easily feasible.

Scale up

The main challenge of this synthesis for a potential application of the material in a photocatalytic process is the low product return, attributed to both the not quantitative yield and the small amount of reagent used. Therefore, scaling up the reaction is crucial, despite challenging, as indicated in the previous paragraph.

In Figure S8, the results obtained are shown by proportionally multiplying each component of the reaction by an arbitrary multiplicative factor. From the results, it can be observed that the reaction maintains good nanoparticle definition up to a 10x factor (Figure 3), while using a 12x factor (Figure S8F) it yields unsatisfactory results.

The sample scaled up to 10x times ("43" in Table S1) was renamed "RD-Cu₂O_10x" and used for further characterisations.

Effect of the Nature of Reagents

In the subsequent paragraphs, the impact of substituting one reactant with a similar counterpart in the reaction mixture conditions will be elucidated. This approach aims to provide a deeper understanding of the individual roles of each component.

Figure 3. FESEM image of RD-Cu₂O_10x.

Cu Precursor

The presence of chloride anions in the reaction environment appears to play a crucial role in facilitating the synthesis of crystalline structures enclosed by {110} crystallographic planes.^[18,32,52,53]

This hypothesis is partially supported by the tests presented in Figure S9, where Cu²⁺ precursors other than CuCl₂ were used, in fact no sample has the same shape definition as sample "25" (Table S1).

The formation of some well-defined rhombododecahedral nanoparticles using nitrate and sulphate (Figure S9A,B) may be attributed to the presence of chloride anions originating from NH₂OH·HCl. Indeed, by reversing the order of NaOH and NH₂OH·HCl addition, thereby reducing the time for the copper anion exchange reaction, both cases resulted in non-defined Cu₂O particles (Figure S9E,F). Using acetate and carbonate as precursors (Figure S9 C,D), the majority of the sample exhibited the synthesis of nanoparticles with an uncontrolled shape, even with the usual order of reagent addition. This outcome is likely due to the greater coordination of these anions to the copper ion, which hinders anionic exchange.

Unfortunately, there are still no clues about the real mechanism involving chlorine ions. The current hypothesis is that chlorine ions could be adsorbed on the surface presenting more exposed copper atoms, *i.e.* {110}, and stabilising it.

Additionally, in Figure S9D, a predominant presence of unreacted Cu(OH)₂ derived from the precursor is noticeable (also detectable in the XRD pattern in Figure S1, entry "48"), suggesting that it may not be an intermediate in the reaction. Instead, it is more likely that a complex, such as Cu(OH)₄²⁻, could be involved. The synthesis of Cu₂O from Cu(OH)₂ observed in some studies is likely dependent on a basic environment, which can facilitate the equilibrium in [Equation (2)].^[54]

Otherwise, this reaction is not permitted in the slightly acidic environment reported here, which is advantageous because Cu(OH)₂ specie is closely related to the side reaction synthesis of CuO according to reaction in [Equation (3)].

Base

To investigate the impact of different bases on the synthesis, two additional bases, NH₄OH and KOH, were tested.

The use of NH₄OH resulted in the failure of the reaction, potentially attributed to the formation of the stable [Cu(NH₃)₄(H₂O)₂]²⁺ complex. This complex is challenging to reduce, as evidenced by the deep blue coloration of the solution upon the addition of NH₄OH, darker than that with NaOH, and characteristic of the complex.^[55]

Substituting NaOH with KOH resulted in the successful synthesis of nanoparticles. However, it led to the formation of well-defined rhombododecahedral nanoparticles that were larger than those obtained with NaOH. Additionally, larger and nearly spherical particles were observed, as illustrated in Figure S9G. This outcome suggests either a more substantial role of the sodium cation Na^+ in determining the rhombododecahedral shape compared to the K^+ ion, or it may indicate a potentially detrimental effect of the latter.

Reducing Agent

Finally, to confirm that $\text{NH}_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{HCl}$ is the only suitable reducing agent for this shape-controlled reaction, two tests were conducted using the other two classical reductants commonly employed for Cu_2O nanoparticles synthesis: glucose and ascorbic acid. An adequate volume of HCl 1 M/ NaOH 5 M was added to the solution immediately after introducing the reducing agent to achieve the desired pH.

Using glucose, the reaction failed, and no detectable Cu_2O nanoparticles were formed, possibly due to the slightly acidic environment and/or the low temperature employed.

On the other hand, employing ascorbic acid resulted in the synthesis of nanoparticles with an undefined shape. (Figure S9H)

These tests further confirm that $\text{NH}_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{HCl}$ is crucially involved in the shape-controlled synthesis, as previously outlined by Huang *et al.*^[24,51]

Reaction Mechanism

According to literature and the tests reported here, the most probable Cu_2O nanoparticles synthesis mechanism is presented from [Equation (4)] to [Equation (6)].

It is essential to note that reactions [Equation (4)] and [Equation (5)] likely occur instantaneously upon the addition of NaOH, facilitated by the dispersion of $\text{NH}_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{HCl}$ in the reaction batch. Meanwhile the nucleation event [Equation (6)] is spontaneous at the right concentration and the shape-dependent particle growth [Equation (7)] constitutes the rate-determining step.

This final step critically depends on the relative stability of the different crystallographic faces. SDS, NH_2OH , and Cl^- are the

key agents responsible for this, but only at very specific relative and absolute concentrations.

The dual role of SDS is the most well-known and easily explainable, even based on previously reported studies.^[22,24,51] Firstly, it slows down the synthesis of nanoparticles by coordinating the copper ions present in the solution (without SDS, the colour change of the reaction occurs in less than 10 minutes, indicating a faster reaction) and releasing them gradually; slowing down the growth is crucial in obtaining well-defined particles, as outlined in section 1.1.

Secondly, it actively coordinates the {110} crystallographic face, inhibiting particle growth in that direction and simultaneously protecting it from etching by the acidic environment. The preference for coordination to the {110} face is attributable to a greater exposure of copper cations on the surface compared to other faces, well stabilised by the coordination with SDS. The role of the chloride anions seems similar, enhancing the selectivity of the facet-controlled synthesis.

Numerous studies have reported the action of this anion on the stability of the {110} face, confirmed by the present study, showing how it is crucial for the formation of rhombic dodecahedral-shaped particles.^[31,56–58]

Moreover, a recent computational study suggests that the adsorbed chloride anion acts as a local defect on the Cu_2O facets, changing their surface energy.^[59] In particular it is shown how the energy of the {110} surface decrease upon the adsorption of the chloride anion on the exposed copper anions, resulting better stabilised than other facets.

Finally, the role of the $\text{NH}_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{HCl}$ molecule needs to be clarified.

It primarily provides electrons to copper by oxidising itself to N_2 [Equation (5)], creates the slightly acidic environment necessary for the reaction, and introduces additional chloride ions, which are crucial for the facet selectivity, as explained above.

However, its relative concentration (compared to the copper precursor) is equally important: at the same pH, an excess of it causes the formation of undefined particles, as showed in Section 1.3.3. Furthermore, it cannot be excluded that it plays a co-stabilising role on the surface, together with SDS and the chloride ion.

Possible side reactions, presented below, are probably inhibited by the templating agents that protect the particles from etching [Equation(8)]^[22] and by the speed at which reaction occurs ([Equation (9)] and [Equation (10)]), as mentioned above.

Optical and EPR Characterisation

In Figure 4 the optical and electronic characterizations performed on the optimised sample RD- Cu_2O _10x, are presented.

Figure 4. DRS calculated absorption spectrum (A) and calculated bandgap using a Tauc Plot-like method (B, inset) of the sample RD-Cu₂O_{10x}.

This sample was obtained according to the indication reported in table S1. The investigation by Diffuse Reflectance (DR) UV-VIS spectroscopy (Figure 4A,B) shows a classical absorption behaviour and a calculated direct bandgap of 2.07 eV, in accordance with previously reported data^[60]. The band gap has been calculated using the Tauc Plot-like method. The UV-vis spectroscopy of Cu²⁺ ion differs from that of Cu⁺ because the latter has a closed shell configuration, while the former has an incomplete d shell configuration. This implies that in the sample containing Cu⁺ where no d-d transitions are expected, the colour is due to the electron transfer between 3 d-4p bands,^[61,62] while a sample containing Cu²⁺ species is coloured because of the presence of the typical d-d transitions. In the figure the typical absorption curve due to the d-d transition of Cu(II) at 550 nm is not so evident and only a shoulder is present at that wavelength due to the very low concentration of copper Cu²⁺ present in the sample.

The ATR spectrum in Figure 5 shows the typical strong mode of vibration of the Cu–O bond at 611 cm⁻¹ and the modes of stretching and bending of the O–H bond, due to water adsorption, at 3445 and 1631 cm⁻¹ respectively. Besides these expected modes is possible to see other vibration which may be associated with hydrocarbons adsorbed on the surface: C–H and C=C bonds bending (810–1000, 1379, 1478 cm⁻¹), C–O

Figure 5. ATR spectrum of the sample RD-Cu₂O_{10x}.

bond stretching (1249 cm⁻¹) and C–H bond stretching (3244–3385 cm⁻¹). These hydrocarbons are strongly adsorbed on the surface and cannot be removed, even after several washes with ethanol, acetone, acetonitrile or hexane, and this should be considered when using these particles for catalytic reactions.

After the synthesis, in Cu₂O rhombic dodecahedral nanoparticles, the presence of some Cu²⁺ ions is always observed, mostly due to the numerous dangling bonds on the surface. The presence of Copper (II) has been evaluated by the Electron Paramagnetic Resonance (EPR) spectroscopy which is able to identify and quantify these ions. Cu⁺, being a 3d¹⁰ ion, is diamagnetic and silent in this technique, meanwhile Cu²⁺ ions are paramagnetic (3d⁹ configuration) and give a typical signal in the EPR spectrum, as shown in Figure 6.

The quantification of Cu²⁺ ions, determined through double integration of the signal in the spectrum (spin-counting), reveals that they constitute 2,9% of all the copper ions in the analysed sample. It's worth noting that the quantification may be overestimated due to the presence of a carbon signal (the carbon presence is revealed through the ATR spectrum), which is masked by the copper signal in the EPR spectrum and cannot be eliminated. Therefore, it is accounted for during integration.

The reported EPR spectrum of Cu²⁺ is essentially similar to the majority of spectra observed for cupric ions in both molecular and solid-state compounds. These typically feature Cu²⁺ in variously distorted octahedral or square planar symmetries. In such cases, as expected, the spin-Hamiltonian parameters exhibit an axial structure ($g_{xx} \approx g_{yy} \approx g_{\perp}$; $g_{zz} \approx g_{\parallel}$). The *g* values are higher than the free electron spin value ($g_e = 2.0023$), following the order $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > g_e$. The hyperfine coupling tensor, resulting from the $I = 3/2$ nuclear spin of ⁶³Cu and ⁶⁵Cu which splits each resonance into four lines, has the structure $A_{\parallel} > A_{\perp}$. In this specific case the perpendicular features are not well resolved so it is not possible to evaluate correctly the value for the A_{\perp} but the shape is in line with the well-known EPR signal for copper ions.^[63,64]

Figure 6. EPR spectrum of the sample RD-Cu₂O_{10x}.

XPS analysis

The elemental composition and chemical states of the sample RD-Cu₂O_10x were further examined using X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS), as shown in Figure 7.

The survey spectrum (Figure 7A) confirms the presence of only copper and oxygen in the sample, aside from surface carbon impurities (gold powder was added to the sample prior to measurement as a calibration standard). The high-resolution Cu 2p spectrum (Figure 7B) reveals a Cu⁺ signal at 932.4 eV and confirms the presence of Cu²⁺ ions at 933.7 eV on the particle surface.

Following the method outlined by Mark C. Biesinger,^[65] it has been calculated that Cu²⁺ concentration reaches up to 94.5% in the approximate 10 nm external layer probed by the XPS analysis, indicating that almost all Cu²⁺ ions are located on the surface.

Upon irradiation, these surface Cu²⁺ ions will be reduced to Cu⁺, creating active sites able to perform the catalytic reaction.

The high-resolution O1s spectrum (Figure 7C) can be deconvoluted into four peaks, tentatively assigned to oxygen bonded to Cu⁺ (530.5 eV), oxygen bonded to Cu²⁺ (531.5 eV), carbon-oxygen single bonds (532.4 eV), and hydrogen-oxygen bonds, likely from adsorbed water (533.2 eV).

The high-resolution C1s spectrum (Figure 7D) consists of two components: one at 285 eV, typically associated with C–C or C–H bonds, and the other at 286.6 eV, corresponding to

carbon bonded to oxygen. This corroborates the assignment in the O1s spectrum at 532.4 eV, indicating the presence of carbon impurities also detected by ATR analysis (Figure 5).

The valence band edge value, measured using Ultraviolet Photoelectron Spectroscopy (UPS), was determined to be approximately 0.33 eV (Figure 8A).

By combining this data with the results of the band-gap calculation from the Tauc Plot analysis (Figure 4B), we were able to estimate the conduction band edge value (0.33–2.07 = −1.74 eV) and construct the band alignment of the prepared sample, as illustrated in Figure 8B.

Conclusions

In this study, we performed an in-depth investigation into the synthesis conditions for producing well-defined rhombic dodecahedral nanoparticles, predominantly exposing the highly catalytic active {110} facets, with sizes ranging largely from 200 to 250 nm.

The shape-dependent synthesis was found to be highly sensitive to variations in pH and temperature, enabling fine-tuning of the amount of corner etching of the particles. Optimization of the reaction parameters led to a halving of the required capping agent amount while significantly increasing the yield.

Figure 7. XPS survey spectrum (A) of the sample RD-Cu₂O_10x and high-resolution spectra of Cu2p (B), O1s (C) and C1s (D).

Figure 8. UPS valence band edge analysis (A) and band alignment (B) of the sample RD-Cu₂O_{10x}.

The optimised and scaled up synthesis require 2.0 mmol of CuCl₂, 6.0 mmol of Sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS), 9.6 mmol of NH₂OH·HCl and 7.0 mmol of NaOH added in this order to 400 ml of water at 25 °C.

The optimised synthesis process demonstrated stability during scale-up, and even better results are guessed with a well-designed flow reactor.

The as-prepared Cu₂O rhombic dodecahedral nanoparticles show great promise in photocatalytic reactions, including pollutant degradation, organic coupling reactions, and solar fuel production.

Author Contributions

MC.P. conceived the study. The synthetic chemistry was carried out by L.S., characterizations were performed by L.S. Data analysis and discussion were carried out by all authors. The paper was written and prepared by MC.P, L.S. and T.O.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords: Shape-controlled synthesis · Cuprous oxide · Morphological control · Nanoparticles

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